

THE PURPOSE AND IMPORTANCE STUDY OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE WITH SPECIAL SUBJECTS (TERMINOLOGY) IN NOPHILOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS (READ AND UNDERSTAND PHYSICS)

Tojibayeva Nazokatkhon

Doctor of pedagogical Sciences (PhD) of the Department of Foreign Language in Exact And Natural Directions of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Razoqov Abdurahmon

Student of the direction of teaching physics and astronomy in TSPU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7369245>

Abstract. *This article presents texts and strengthening exercises in science in order to develop and qualifications of students, as well as an integrative approach to a foreign language and a special subject. What is motion? Motion is movement in any direction. You can move up, down, forwards, backwards, and sideways. You can move in circles. You can wiggle, wave, twist, turn, roll, flip, sway, bend, pivot, shake, and spin. You can see all the answer and vocabulary about the theme.*

Key words: *motion, wiggle, wave, twist, turn, roll, flip, sway, bend, pivot.*

At a time when there is a process of globalization, demand and need and attitude towards a foreign language. In connection with the expansion of international relations with the countries, it takes time for specialists working in the field of science, culture and, as well as in other fields, to know one foreign language, and communicate in a foreign language. The supply of personnel for adult specialists in each area is one of the priority directions of the policy of our state. In our country, in last years, the President and the Cabinet of Ministers also that the relevant decisions and decrees are aimed at training qualified personnel in our country. Because no matter which of the modern specialists owns the industry, he can provide information and receive information in a foreign language, this becomes a professional necessity.

In modern conditions, there is no education special training of students to provide special educational various fields of foreign language science (for example: physics, chemistry, biology, geography, economics) in nophylological teachers. The educational area for this industry, professional foreign language for specialists is independently organized by everyone.

Today, along with other subjects education a foreign language, the period when it is necessary to organize for specialists in various fields, dialogue in a foreign language remains one of the important components of their professional activities. Therefore, students are required not only to know a foreign language, but also to freely communicate with colleagues in a foreign language areas. This requires and updating the purpose and content of foreign languages.

The organization of educational for the coordination of a foreign language with special subjects in philological higher countries gives good results in achieving goal. It is necessary to develop coordinated work plans, programs with specialized departments.

In this article, in order to ensure the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 19, 2021 No. 5117 "On measures to bring activities to popularize the education of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level," the use of students directions physics and astronomy in English lessons, development of specialties and at the same time a foreign language created and developed in accordance with the requirements of the standards of the state education, and are also contained them.

This article presents texts and strengthening exercises in science in order to develop and qualifications of students, as well as an integrative approach to a foreign language and a special subject.

*«Measure what is measurable
and make measurable what is not so»*

Galileo

1. What do you know about motion?
2. Is the motion of a ghost an example of motion?
3. Can something stop moving? How would you show it?
4. Does a body moving forever in a straight line show that nature or space is infinite?
5. Can the universe move?

Motion is the most fundamental observation in nature. Everyday motion is predictable and deterministic. Predictability is reflected in six aspects of motion: continuity, conservation, reversibility, mirror-invariance, relativity and minimization. Some of these aspects are valid for all motion, and some are valid only for everyday motion.

The world and the Universe are action-packed. People and animals are always on the move. The planets are constantly circling the Sun. Are there any rules to all this activity? Our world and the whole Universe are governed by the laws of nature. Scientists who try to understand and learn about these laws are called physicists. Here are some questions that physicists across history have wondered about: When you drop a ball, why does it fall on the ground? Why does not it float up? If you spin a top, why does not it spin forever? Why does it eventually stop? Maybe you have wondered about these things, too.

To answer those questions, physicists needed to discover the laws of motion. What is motion? Motion is movement in any direction. You can move up, down, forwards, backwards, and sideways. You can move in circles. You can wiggle, wave, twist, turn, roll, flip, sway, bend, pivot, shake, and spin.

A force is a push or a pull. Here is a simple example: A cat hits a ball with its paw and makes the ball roll across the floor. The cat uses force to make the ball move. When you kick a ball or pull open a door, you are also using force. The more force you use, the faster the object will move.

Speed measures how far an object moves in a certain amount of time. However, things do not always move at the same speed. Forces can cause moving objects to speed up or slow down. «Average speed» equals «distance divided by time».

So why do things in motion slow down and stop after a while? The answer is «friction». Friction is another kind of force. Friction is two things rubbing or sliding against each other. Skis on snow. A car on a road. A ball rolling across a carpet. Friction is a force that slows down moving objects. If you roll a ball across a shaggy rug, you can see that there are lumps and bumps in the rug that make the ball slow down. The rubbing, or friction, between the ball and the rug is what makes the ball stop rolling. But what would happen if you rolled the ball across a very smooth surface and there was no wall or obstacle in the way? Would the ball keep rolling forever? Unfortunately, no. There is no such thing as a «frictionless surface». There is friction between all objects and materials when they are touching.

To the naked eye, an object or surface may look perfectly smooth. If you looked at it under a microscope, you could see the tiny lumps and bumps that create friction when any two objects slide against each other. There is even friction when an object moves through the air. The less friction there is, the longer objects in motion can keep moving. For example, if you pushed off and tried to slide across the sidewalk in sneakers, you would not get very far. There is too much friction between the rubber soles of your sneakers and the rough concrete sidewalk. However, if you wore ice skates and used the same amount of force to push off and slide across an ice rink, you would glide for a long way. There is not much friction between the thin metal blade of an ice skate and the slick ice of the rink.

Some forces are invisible and can make objects move without touching them. You have probably played around with magnets before and know that magnets have an invisible pull—a force that can attract iron and steel objects. A magnet has a «north pole» and a «south pole». If you take two magnets, the north pole of one magnet and the south pole of the other will pull toward each other. If you try to join the north poles of the two magnets, however, the magnets will push each other away. The same is true if you try to put the two south poles together—the magnets will repel each other.

Magnets may seem mysterious because they can pull on other objects and make them move without touching them. It would be wise to mention that there is another invisible force that you interact with every second of every day and you probably take it for granted. That force is gravity. Gravity is the invisible force that holds us to the surface of the Earth.

Earth’s gravity pulls objects toward the center of the Earth. So when you drop a book, it falls to the ground instead of floating away. When you jump up, gravity pulls you back down.

Every object actually has gravity, whether it is the Earth, the Sun, a person, or just a marble. The more «mass» an object has, the stronger its force of gravity. Mass just means how much «stuff» is in an object. Some materials are packed with more stuff than others. For example, steel has more stuff in it than Styrofoam. If two balls are the same size, and one is made of foam and one is made of steel, the steel ball will have greater mass.

The Earth and moon both have gravity that is strong enough to pull them toward each other. Although the moon’s gravity is not as strong as Earth’s, it pulls on the water in our oceans and creates the tides. So, if the Earth and moon are pulled toward each other, why don’t they crash into each other? The moon is held in orbit by the force of Earth’s gravity. The speed of the

moon’s orbit is what prevents the moon from falling down to Earth. If the moon went slower, it would fall to Earth. If it went faster, it would escape the Earth’s gravity and fly off into space.

Isaac Newton was a famous scientist who was interested in all sorts of things, from gravity and the orbits of planets to the rules about how objects move. One of his most important discoveries is called Newton’s First Law of Motion. Using experiment and observation, Newton showed that objects have a tendency to keep doing what they are doing. Objects that are still, stay still. Objects that are moving, keep moving. A still object stays still and a moving object keeps moving in the same straight line, unless a force pushes or pulls it. Whether they are moving or not moving, objects resist changing their «state of motion». This is called inertia.

Inertia is the reason seatbelts are important. If you are in a fast-moving car and the driver slams on the brakes, the car will stop, but you will keep moving forward. The seatbelt stops you, so you do not hit the dashboard or windshield.

Mass vs. weight. The mass of an object stays the same no matter where you are in the Universe. That is because the amount of stuff in the object does not change. Weight is actually the pull of gravity on an object. You feel your weight because the ground is pushing against the pull of gravity. So the weight of an object can change depending on where it is in the Universe. An object that weighs 60 pounds on Earth would weigh only about 10 pounds on the moon because the force of gravity on the moon is only one-sixth as strong as it is on Earth. Although your mass would stay the same, you would feel much lighter on the moon or you would if you did not have to wear that heavy spacesuit.

Air resistance is a kind of friction. Molecules in the air push up against falling bodies while gravity pulls them down. The force of air resistance opposes the force of gravity. The friction created by air resistance is not strong enough to stop falling objects, but it can stop them from speeding up. Thanks to air resistance, falling objects reach a top speed, also called «terminal velocity», that is based on their size and mass.

The concepts of force, motion, gravity, mass, and inertia and more govern the world and our Universe. They are complex ideas but once you understand them, you will see everything a little more clearly.

We also provide you with a dictionary of these words:

VOCABULARY

Word	Pronunciation	Translation
attract, v.	/ə'trækt/	jalb qilmoq; o'ziga tortmoq
average, adj.	/'ævərɪdʒ/	o'rtacha, o'rtacha son; syn. medium
blade, n.	/bleɪd/	olmos, lezviye
brake, n.	/breɪk/	tormoz
bump, v.	/bʌmp/	to'qnshmoq; syn. collide
dashboard, n.	/'dæʃbɔ:d/	asbob-uskuna taxtasi
direction, n.	/dɪ'rekʃən/	yo'nalish
drop, v.	/drɒp/	tomchi tushish
float, v.	/fləʊt/	suv yuzasida suzish
force, n.	/fɔ:s/	kuch

friction, n.	/ˈfrɪkʃən/	ishqalanish
govern, v.	/ˈɡʌvən/	boshqarmoq; idora qilmoq, syn. rule
gravity, n.	/ˈɡrævəti/	tortishish kuchi; syn. gravitation, pull
inertia, n.	/ɪˈnɜːʃə/	inertsiya
invisible, adj.	/ɪnˈvɪzəbl/	ko‘rinmas
iron, n/adj.	/aɪən/	temir
law, n.	/lə:/	qonun
marble, n/adj.	/ˈmɑːbl/	marmar
mass, n.	/mæs/	massa
molecule, n.	/ˈmɒlɪkjʊːl/	molekula, zarra
motion, n.	/ˈməʊʃən/	harakat, syn. movement
obstacle, n.	/ˈɒbstəkl/	to‘siq, xalaqit syn. hindrance, obstruction
orbit, n.	/ˈɔːbɪt/	orbita
paw, n.	/pɔː/	panja
pole, n.	/pəʊl/	qutb
pull, v.	/pʊl/	tortish
push, v.	/pʊʃ/	itarish
resistance, n.	/rɪˈzɪstəns/	qarshilik
rink, n.	/rɪŋk/	muz maydoni
roll, v.	/rəʊl/	o‘ramoq, dumaloqlamoq
rub, v.	/rʌb/	surtish
rug, n.	/rʌɡ/	gilamcha
seatbelt, n.	/siːt belt/	havfsizlik kamari
shaggy, adj.	/ˈʃæɡ.i/	junli, serjun
slide, v.	/slɑɪd/	sirpanmoq, toymoq
smooth, adj.	/smuːð/	silliq
speed, n.	/spiːd/	tezlik
spin, v.	/spɪn/	aylanish
surface, n.	/ˈsɜːfɪs/	sirt, yuza
terminal, adj.	/ˈtɜːmɪnəl/	oxirgi
tide, n.	/taɪd/	to‘lqin
universe, n.	/ˈjuːnɪvɜːs/	borliq
velocity, n.	/vɪˈləsəti/	tezlik (vektor)
weight, n.	/weɪt/	Vazn

REFERENCES

1. M.N.Sayfullina, N.M.Xabirova, English for physicists. Kazan 2016
2. T.V. Kornaukhova, S.V. Kuznetsova, V.Yu. Murzina, Great physicists. Penza 2014
3. Rutherford: <http://teachmen.ru>
4. The Standard Model of Particle Physics: www.benbest.com